

ROLE OF WOMEN IN GOOD GOVERNANCE

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ABSTRACT - The concept of "good" governance requires making normative decisions about what constitutes the legal appropriation and efficient exercise of authority. Some organisations that offer outside assistance and social activists view good governance as implying democratic governance, which implies a focus on participation, human rights, and social justice. Some people simply refer to it as managing the nation's endowments of natural and human resources in a way that produces public goods (such as security and justice) and distributes them in a way that fosters economic growth and human development. Others use the term to describe the creation of public goods. IFIs (International Financial Institutions) have a more constrained perspective on governance. In their eyes, "good governance" is more about the effectiveness of the state than it is about the justice of the economic system or the legitimacy of the political system. Decision-makers' ability to act to improve the suffering of disadvantaged women or address the problem of gender inequality depends on how policies are implemented in practise. The process has only just begun with the signing of international agreements and the enactment of laws addressing issues like women's rights, equal access to education, marital rape, and credit and property ownership. Legislation and policy must be understood in terms of governmental directives, funding allotments, institutional arrangements, operational procedures, and monitoring standards. The concept of "governance" clarifies the link between political commitment and the successful and efficient implementation of programmes. Reform efforts for governance systems have received a lot of attention recently and are still receiving attention now on a national and international level.

Keywords: Women, Governance, Democratic, Decentralization and Power.

1. INTRODUCTION

Governance" can be defined in a variety of ways, from a narrow concentration on economic management to a more expansive definition that includes political liberalisation and the decrease of social inequality. The WB defines governance as "the manner in which the State exerts and gains authority." The ability of the state to exert authority and the responsibility it faces as a result are the two main components of governance for policymakers. A state's hardware consists of its financial capacity, its physical and administrative infrastructure for delivering public goods, the size and skill of its workforce, and the efficiency with which budgeting and policymaking processes are conducted. Equipment for a state. Capacity encompasses all things. Any system in which certain players have the power to solicit answers from others and decide whether or not misconduct is acknowledged and punished is referred to as "software." According to the authors, gender equality and women's participation in decision-making are two measures to enhance sustainable development. The application of a gender-inclusive approach. Women's engagement in the workforce and decision-making is becoming increasingly important in today's society. Good governance necessitates that all stakeholders be involved in the process of making decisions. With that in mind, where a large percentage of the workforce is made up of women, their participation in decision-making should be considered as a means of ensuring gender equality. Gender mainstreaming and women's involvement is a significant problem in India, and this article examines some of the most important

measures for improving women's participation and gender mainstreaming. Indian democracy was modelled after that of the British Parliament, which was founded on the principle of universal adult franchise. One of India's greatest accomplishments is that it is a fully functioning democracy.

Women make up nearly half the population, although they hold less than 10% of the country's parliamentary seats, a fact that should not be ignored. It was established in 1971 that a committee on the Status of Women would study women's issues. Even though women make up the majority of the population, a 1974 assessment by the group Towards Equality stated that their influence in politics was negligible. As a corrective measure. According to the committee's recommendations, each party should field a certain number of female candidates. Measures were taken to ensure that women were given a seat on municipal and panchayat boards, as well as the ability to vote in 1992. Conversely to this, the Women's Reservation Bill is still stuck in government debate and inaction.

2. RESEARCH OBJECTIVES

Women's involvement in politics promotes gender equality and has an impact on the variety of policy concerns that are taken into consideration as well as the types of solutions that are put forth. The study's objective is to describe and analyse the significance of gender mainstreaming in good governance for the nation's overall growth. The study's main focus is on how gender engagement in decision-making through consensus-building and representation leads to women's empowerment directly.

3. MATERIAL AND METHOD

This research paper is mostly based on secondary sources of information, including research papers, books, and official documents downloaded from affairs website, one of the official portals of the Indian government. An empirical methodology has been used to analyse and explain the facts and relationship critically. To get a just conclusion, qualitative data were gathered and used. For this research investigation, direct approaches including scientific observation and expert interviewing have also been used. Focus has been placed on empiricism, observation, critical analysis, and exploratory methodologies to contextualise the study's subject matter. With the use of such approaches, new, rational, and empirically supported information has been added to the body of literature

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

According to Abraham Lincoln, a government that is administered by, by, and for its people constitutes a true democracy. It is questionable whether or not the majority of democracies' governments actually reflect all of society's varied interests and are answerable to all of their constituents. Achieving true democracy necessitates addressing the low female participation rate, which is of particular concern to democracies. Women must take part in the decision-making process in order to guarantee that the interests of women are represented in government. In general, the state will not interfere with inclusive or democratic governing arrangements that do not include women. For gender equality in the workplace and policymaking to advance, women's participation in local government is crucial. Due to the diversity of demands and viewpoints that women have on social and political issues, including them in policy and decision-making processes is crucial. A woman is knowledgeable about typical problems because of her role in the family and community. They thus acquire a fresh perspective that could aid in their long-term achievement. Local government women have a responsibility to dismantle gender stereotypes in society and the public sphere and to encourage other women to pursue a variety of vocations. People started to embrace women as public administrators and local government officials after witnessing how they benefited others. Society acknowledges women's dedication, integrity, and opposition to criminalising politics. In order to identify areas where policy can be improved, it is essential to evaluate the level of political engagement of women. India has collected records on female involvement since the nation gained its freedom. For instance, infrastructure is being established to track women's involvement in municipal government.

4.1 Participation and good governance

Good governance doesn't have a standard definition or range of application. There are several uses for the words "governance" and "good governance." The rule of law, regulatory framework, and economic policies all fall under the category of governance (IMF, 2013). Three significant aspects of governance are: Choosing leaders, managing public affairs, and the capacity of the government to control resources and create and carry out policies are the first two. The term emphasises the

capacity of the government apparatus to create policies and provide services, as well as the legitimacy of the executive and legislative branches of power. Transparency, accountability, participation, and responsiveness are necessary for successful governance, according to the UN High Commissioner for Human Rights (to the needs of the people). The term "governance" also describes the way decisions are made and carried out (or not carried out) (UNESCAP, 2009). According to this definition, the fundamental component of effective governance refers to the decision-making process, the manner in which decisions are carried out, and the individuals involved. Women's engagement in senior management in public organisations will be emphasised by good governance. Even though many women work outside the home in a variety of professions and sectors, few are active in top management decision-making. When women make major contributions to the workforce, it is essential that they participate in decision-making to ensure that women's issues are properly addressed and that the women's agenda is pushed. Having a voice in decision-making, whether directly or through reputable intermediary organisations that represent their interests, is referred to as participation. Freedom of association, speech, and constructive participation are necessary for such extensive engagement (UNDP, 1997). This article will assess women's involvement in high-level decision-making, as per the definition.

4.2 Gender Mainstreaming

The UN Economic and Social Council (ECOSOC) have approved the following official defining idea for GM:

Mainstreaming a gender viewpoint is the process of examining how proposed policies, laws, and programmes would affect men and women equally. The formulation and implementation of policies and programmes, as well as monitoring and assessment in all spheres of the political, economic, and social spheres, must take into account the perspectives and experiences of women and men if equality is to be achieved and inequality to be avoided. Gender mainstreaming has made it easier for women to participate more actively in all spheres of life. Gender Mainstreaming was first proposed as a way to advance gender equality on a global scale during the Fourth World Conference on Women in Beijing in 1995. It entails taking into account how all proposed actions, such as laws, rules, and projects, might impact both women and

men. Considering that half of the world's population are women, gender mainstreaming was created to ensure that women receive the same benefits as males. Planning, putting into practise, and evaluating social, political, and economic action are all part of gender mainstreaming. A typical implementation involves "internal" organisational changes as well as "external" operational adjustments. The former refers to changes that must be made in organisations' structures and practises in order to embrace gender mainstreaming values and goals.

The inclusion of gender equality will be expected of policymakers through the restructuring of policy procedures. By using this strategy, gender preconceptions will be eradicated and policies will be redirected to support gender equality. To achieve gender equality and good governance, which are gauged by the inclusion of women in decision-making, gender mainstreaming is crucial.

4.3 Women participation in decision making

Women are frequently powerful change agents who encourage others to take action, assert their rights, strengthen their communities, and protect the environment. Their involvement is essential to democracy. Women continue to be underrepresented in leadership positions and with equal authority in corporate boardrooms and presidential cabinets. Limitations on education, resources, and free time are sexist and prevent women from advancing. The percentage of female legislators has increased from 11 to just over 21 percent since 1995. At the current rate of development, gender parity won't be achieved in governments, parliaments, or peace negotiations until the next century. The participation of women is equal. They can help whole societies as leaders. According to the Inter-Parliamentary Union, female legislators provide social welfare, legal protection, and trust more consideration. Upholding the commitments made in Beijing and promoting female leadership may improve equal participation. In India, prejudice against women persists despite numerous laws protecting their rights. According to UNDP, women's involvement in decision-making is a crucial component. To promote gender equality, two strategies are required. The first tactic is the promotion and defence of women's human rights and fundamental freedoms as well as their participation in organisational decision-making. The most fundamental measures to measure women's political participation are voting

percentage and legislative elections. It is challenging to estimate women's participation in decision-making.

4.5 Gender equality and governance reform

Legislation promoting gender equality cannot be passed or put into effect until gender competency and responsibility issues are resolved. Gender issues are unlikely to be resolved by focusing just on market power and property rights in governance reform; on the contrary, they might even become more entrenched. If institutions, organisations, and procedures are not sufficiently changed or rebuilt during the reform process to strategically address gender imbalance, it will return. Gender equality hasn't always been prioritised when it comes to effective government. Women's engagement and gender equity were only included in the early World Bank declarations on governance transformation in relation to human rights. In transforming government organisations, there are gender-specific skill gaps. The needs of women are not taken into consideration when allocating cash for public purposes. Men who are against gender equality may predominate in the public service or court. In a moment of budgetary restriction, workers at the bottom of state bureaucracies in the public sector might be the first to be let go. The "rule of law" measures designed to stabilise the business sector may limit women's ability to secure assets over which they have customary rights or profit from illegal private activity. A lack of resources to analyse bills or accounts by gender may be the cause of the underrepresentation of women in legislative oversight positions. Those in positions of authority should uphold gender equity in their actions in public and make sure that women are represented in institutions of accountability by enacting gender-sensitive reforms. In respect to the involvement and nomination of men and women, investigation methodology, evidence use, probity, and fairness must all be considered. Any organization's bylaws or articles of formation must expressly forbid gender inequality.

4.6 Gender and Accountability

Governance discussions should take gender-specific accountability shortcomings into account. Holders of public office should uphold gender equality legislation and standards. Even electoral institutions have underlying gender biases that prevent the selection of representatives who would advance gender-equity goals, despite the fact that electoral institutions are supposed to operate

impartially and gender-neutrally. According to research, governmental bureaucracies have a marked gender asymmetry in their employment distribution, with much more women employed at lower levels than at higher ones. It is challenging to find comparable cross-national data on women's employment and standing in public sector hierarchies. According to ILO data, women make up 10-20% of the workforce in education and health, and less than 10% of the workforce in "public administration, military, and social security." 13. Only a small number of state-socialist, developing, and Caribbean nations have significantly higher rates. It might be reduced in industries like mining or transportation where women are uncommon but overworked. Downsizing initiatives have been disastrous in countries like Vietnam where the proportion of women working in the public sector is high. Women made about 70% of those laid off in state-owned companies in the early 1990s. Women may lose more jobs than men at the lowest levels of public services. Gender-sensitive public sector change has been given top priority by women's organisations and international organisations.

5. CONCLUSION

Each and every one of us values good governance. If the government is open, responsible, and simple for the general public to grasp, then citizens are happy to pay for high-quality public services. Gandhi's "Antodaya" ideal must be the focal point of our nation's policy if we are to restore effective government in the nation. When the women's movement challenges and engages with governmental institutions, women are more likely to participate in democratic processes and achieve collective power. When it comes to women's right to accessible, safe abortion, the outcome of many elections is in doubt. Legislators, judges, and other members of the judiciary have continued to act despite this. This incidence is unusual. Institutions and movements are organised in descending order with power centralised at the top. In more powerful institutions, women are less influential. The percentage of female members of parliament is lower than the percentage of female members of local administrative bodies. Women are more active locally than they are on a national level. In local governments and organisations like school boards, municipal councils, and civic clubs, a lot of women are elected to executive roles. These

initiatives have increased the status of motherhood in the community (opposing the dumping of toxic waste in their communities, deforestation, and violence in their communities). Local communities are less affected by national institutions and movements. People argue over the issue of whether women who were elected to panchayats as a result of their institutional involvement or activism carry out their duties. Women's movements must exert greater pressure at higher levels in order to bring about change.

Women are more likely to demonstrate leadership in groups rather than alone, and local organisations provide more opportunity for this than global movements. Quotas are one technique to ensure that there are enough women in leadership positions to adequately represent their interests. Institutions and activities that address the distinction between one's private and public life are more popular among women. This is a common occurrence when governmental rules make it impossible for people to carry out their home obligations. The increased informality of local rather than national contexts may also account for the greater participation of women at the local level. When it comes to open and democratic forums, women are more likely to participate. Women's participation necessitates the formation of democratic deliberative bodies that exist only occasionally at the national and municipal levels.

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